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An assessment of the relationship between headmasters' leadership and teachers' performance in Makindye division, Kampala district, Uganda

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Abstract

Leadership style practiced by the school headmasters is a key issue in managing performance in schools. This study was to establish the assessment of the relationship between the headmasters' leadership styles and the secondary teachers' performance in secondary schools in Makindye division. The hypothesis of the study was tested, that; there is no significant relationship between the headmasters' leadership style and the teachers' performance in Makindye division secondary schools. The study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches with descriptive and correlation research designs. The study found that, the nature of secondary headmasters' leadership style used in Makindye division is highly democratic with (average mean=3.149, SD=0.849) and autocratic with (average mean=2.446, SD=1.108). The study results indicated that there is a strong positive relationship between the headmasters' leadership styles and teachers' performance in Makindye division with ($r = -.352^{**}$, $p = 0.000$ less than 0.05 level of significance). The study hypothesis was rejected and hence accepted the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant relationship between headmasters' leadership styles and teachers' performance in Makindye division secondary schools, since the P-Value was 0.000 less than 0.05 level of significance.

Keywords: Assessment; Relationship; Leadership; Styles; Teachers; Performance

1. Introduction

Teachers' performance is very important in the effectiveness of the school management in order to achieve the set goals and objectives, the teachers should be able to perform their responsibility in order to help the schools achieve the goals and objectives (Goddy, 2017; Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demiraglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021). Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), explain teachers' performance as the overall expected value from teachers' behaviour carried out for a period of time. The role of the headmasters and their teachers is very important in this regard in regarding performance of the school. (Abbas, Saud, Ekousti, 2020); Atasoy, 2020; Abbas, Saud, Ekousti, 2020; Atasoy, 2020). However rapid changes in the environment and organizations over the past years have resulted into new type of leadership that calls for less and more democracy, needed to ensure survival of organization as supported by (Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiiimwe & Niyikiza, 2023). According to Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), a good and responsible leader attempts to change the attitudes and actions of people that are related to specific goals and not attitudes or actions that are not related to goal (Asiiimwe & Zuena, 2023; Apiku & Asiiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiiimwe & Apiku, 2023).

To achieve set goals, the head teachers should conclude that teachers say their thoughts and should be treated fairly in their working environment (Asiiimwe & Zuena, 2023; Apiku & Asiiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiiimwe & Apiku, 2023). Besides this, they are able to make claims (Demiraglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah, 2021). Participation in school

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leadership is important to motivate both teachers and learners. It is noted that teachers behave in different ways under various situations due to poor handling (Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023). Identifying the teachers needs the headmasters can encourage effective leadership in schools, enhancing better teaching performance among teachers. The effectiveness of the headmasters' leadership roles has been a matter of concern to many educationists that need attention (Hague & Yamooah, 2021; (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023).

Leadership style to have a good set of approaches, qualities and skills in the headmasters, the following factors are needed; values, trusting employees, leadership direction, and a sense of security shaped in important situations (Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023). Every head teacher should perform the main tasks in a way that have differences with others, Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) say that schools need effective leadership style to give good results and bring satisfaction to teachers and learners; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023). In European countries like, Germany, Britain and Norway, the teachers are committed to their teaching duties because they are motivated. The teachers of these countries manage their time, and regularly attend to their working stations because of the good leadership, Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021; Parveen, et al, 2022; (Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Niyikiza, 2023). According to Parveen, et al (2022) in his research conducted in Dubai, teachers' performance is improved by the leadership styles applied by the school administrators.

In countries like in Australia, UK, USA, the performance of teachers was reinforced by the performance and development culture accreditation scheme, released in 2004 as part of the Blueprint reform in public schools, aimed to promote greater consistency between schools' performance appraisal process as each school sought accreditation and proved that their school had key performance and development processes in place (Ozgenel, 2020). The teacher's performance according to some literature and recommendations, improves when the following conditions are present: opportunities for teacher self-reflection, recognition and goal setting (Hague & Yamooah 2021), regular classroom observation and the provision of constructive feedback from school leader or managers and peers (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023). Regular feedback on classroom performance as an ongoing dialogue should be done daily (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021). Training and mentoring from peers and leaders and opportunities to contribute to, and engage in team work, collaboration and action learning with the teachers should be done to maintain quality management (Hague & Yamooah 2021; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023). .

As a part of the agenda to drive quality teaching in countries like Australia schools, a National Performance and Development Framework that outlines key aspects of a performance reviews has been done (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021). This has helped to evaluate and develop teachers in their performance in all the activities. Leadership styles vary depending on the situation (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023. Parveen, et al (2022) show that, task-oriented leadership style is appropriate when the situation is either extreme favourable or extremely unfavourable to the leader. The favourable situation exists when the situation is moderately favourable, a people-oriented leadership style is appropriate (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023).

Fielder's contingency model supports that, group performance or effectiveness is dependent upon interaction between the leadership style and the amount of control that the supervisor has over the situation (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021). The contingency model was the most influential model of leadership in 1980s worldwide. Its approach includes four sets of concepts that need to be considered, like; teachers' traits, characteristics of the situation, behaviour and effectiveness of the leader (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; (Hague & Yamooah 2021: Asiimwe & Niyikiza, 2023).

According to Parveen, et al (2022) the path goal theory emphasizes on how the leader can facilitate a task performance by showing subordinates how performance can be instrumental in achieving rewards. This theory explains that people are satisfied with their work and will work hard if they believe what their work will lead to things that are valued. The theory further focuses on what leaders should do to motivate and inspire people so that the employees can perform well. Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), path goal theory manifests the function of the leader, is to clarify and set the goals with subordinates and help them to find the best path of achieving their goals and remove obstacles. Path goal theory becomes unique for the reasons that motivation aspects are not discussed by any other leadership theory but only path goal theory which also identifies four theoretical types of leadership which are identified as, directive, supportive, and participative and achievement orientation. However, the theory does not propose one best way to lead but suggests that, the appropriate style will depend on the situational analysis per the time.

In the sub Saharan Africa, the teachers' performance is not all that good because of various factors; poor reward management, salaries, allowances and different management styles by school administrators (Parveen, et al, 2022). In Nigeria, Ghana, Zambia and South Africa, teachers' performance is important factor in the development of the school and attention is given to teachers' wellbeing. The way the teachers work affects the school either positively or negatively (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). Head teachers should make sure that teachers perform to their expectations by using different leadership styles like democratic to have positive results from their teachers. Accordingly, not all leadership styles have a positive impact on the teachers, other leadership styles have got a negative impact on teachers' performance like autocratic (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). Asiimwe and Zuena, (2023) indicate that the more interpersonally skilful and the good leadership available in a school the better the performance of the school. According to Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), effective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment are the types of commitment levels teachers should have for better performance (Parveen, et al, 2022; peers (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023; Mugenyi, Asiimwe & Apiku, 2023).

In East Africa, there are still many challenges of leadership style, used in secondary schools which affect teachers' performance. Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), there has been a debate with the school leaders on the concern with regards to decide which leadership style is to effect performance in schools. Differences in leadership style used by head teachers have been raised in performance of schools in which some perform better, while others perform poorly (Liebowitz, 2019; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). Conflicts between head teachers and their teachers occur in schools because of the leadership style they apply in their schools, like; teachers' absenteeism, persistence in drinking alcohol during working hours, are related to heartaches' leadership style. It was discovered that very few schools which perform better in Makindye secondary schools are those that their leaders apply democratic style of leadership.

2. Related literature

Every leader in every school performs certain roles/tasks for the smooth running of the organizational performance. As a result Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), say that it's the work of the head teacher for influencing people so that they can strive willingly and enthusiastically towards the accomplishment of goals. According to (Liebowitz, 2019), leadership means influencing people to work willingly with zeal towards the achievements of the school goal. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) define leadership style as an ingredient of personality embedded in leaders that cause subordinates to follow them (Liebowitz, 2019; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023).

On the other hand defines leadership style to a particular behaviour used by the leader to motivate subordinates to achieve the objectives of the school. Therefore, the school headmaster is supposed control the school resources for the purpose of achieving the educational goals, for the development and school progress (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). Leaders express leadership in different ways according to their roles, like; formulating aims and objective, establishing structures, managing and motivating personnel and providing leadership Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020), claiming that, providing leadership is a very essential part of the leaders' role. The leadership style the leaders use determines whether will accomplish the task at hand or not, and whether the leader will be able to achieve and maintain positive relationship with the staff (Asiimwe and Zuena, 2023).

2.1.1. Democratic Leadership

Democratic leadership style refers to a situation where there is an equal work among the leaders and the subordinates. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) democratic organizations typically have the following characteristics; policies are determined by a group of people, technical and job performance measures are discussed by all, leaders provide advice to members in regards to implementing tasks, members are also free to choose with whom they work. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020); state that, the leaders using the democratic style build a consensus by participation, also expecting a high level of excellence and self-direction (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). In democratic leadership, there is a high degree of staff morale and people are willing to work because they are motivated (Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) suggest that the leader can behave in different ways in different situations. For example, the headmaster who uses the democratic leadership style, has the mentioned kind of behaviour like; use of directive style, supportive style, participative, consultative and achievement-oriented style that can improve performance.

According to Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) maintains that a good democratic leader encourages participation and delegates wisely but never loses sight of the fact that he/she values group discussion and input from his/her team. Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) however, like

other styles, democratic leadership style is not always appropriate. It is the most successful when used with highly skilled and experienced employees and employers when implementing operational or resolving individuals or group problems and challenges. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) say that democratic leadership style is most effective when the leader wants to keep employees to share the decision making and problem solving duties.

Shared leadership theory is used in democratic style, and the shared leadership theory is formed from the task-oriented factors such as; planning, management, problem solving and relationship-oriented factors such as supporting and consideration as well as develop and mentoring (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023). According to Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) leaders manage the task-oriented planning and administration by sharing to develop objectives and strategies involving participation in decision making, setting targets and determining how to use human resources in an efficient manner.

Head teachers in their hierarchy and the mode in which decision making is conducted, a number of leadership styles could be identified together with the reasons to why leaders may lead in different ways. It is certain that different styles of leadership are needed to enable the school to implement the curriculum in boarding and non-boarding schools, and be able to meet the objective of preparing learners holistically. This can improve the objective based education (OBE). It should be noted that, the significance of using different leadership styles depends on the context of the tasks or activities at a given time (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023). (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023).

Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asimwe and Zuena (2023) explain that, distributive leadership style is best understood as the practice over leaders, followers and their situation and incorporates the activities of multiple groups of individuals. This shows that a social distribution of leadership where the leadership function is stretched over the work of a number of individuals; is an alternative perspective to a heroic leader. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) tried to describe a distributive leadership theory advocate that school's dissenter the leadership. In this sense leadership is more appropriately understood as fluid and emergent, rather than a fixed phenomenon. Teacher leadership emphasis is upon collective action, empowerment and shared agency are reflected in distributive leadership theory. Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) describe distributive leadership style as it is one of the leadership styles which in one way or another allow members of the school organization to participate in leadership.

2.1.2. Autocratic leadership

Abbas, Saud, Ekousti (2020); Atasoy (2020) found that autocratic tend to have some following characteristics; leaders don't consult members of the organization in their decision making, the leader sets all policies, the leader is the only that determines the methods of work, the leader determines the duties of the followers and the leader specifies technical and performance evaluation standards. The autocratic leadership style is also known as authoritarian style, where power and decision making depend entirely on one person (leader). The leader directs group members on the way things should be done, and doesn't give clear channel or communication between him/her and the subordinates (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023).

You might say it is a request that induces compliance or obedience, which is automatic, we really don't think much about it, and we just do it. Moreover, Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asimwe and Zuena (2023) suggest that autocratic leadership can include the following situation; new untrained employees who do not know which tasks to perform or which procedures to follow; require effective supervision. This can be provided only through detailed order and instructions. Employees compelled not to respond to any other leadership style. This is so because, there is a limited time in which to make a decision and manager power is challenged by an employee. In this type of leadership, interactions between heads of schools and teachers are one-way communication. The role of the teacher is to implement the order.

2.1.3. Laissez-faire leadership

Laissez-faire style is described by Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asimwe and Zuena (2023) as the most effective style, especially where followers are mature and highly motivated. Laissez-faire leadership style allows complete freedom to group decision without the leader's participation. Thus, subordinates are free to do what they like and the role of the leader is to avail materials. The leader doesn't interfere with or participate in the cause of events determined by the group (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023).

Laissez-faire gives authority to employees to perform without being forced. Subordinates are allowed to work as they wish themselves, with a minimum supervision or no interference (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023). Authority and power are given to the employees and they must determine goals, make decisions and resolve problems on their own where necessary. Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asimwe and Zuena (2023) estate that, the laissez-faire leader uses his/her power very little, if at all, giving the subordinates a degree of independence in their operations. Such leaders depend largely on the subordinates to set their own goals and the means of achieving them.

Again Lunenburg and Ornestem (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asimwe and Zuena (2023) maintain that laissez-faire leaders avoid expressing their views and taking action on important issues and they fail to make or at least delay decisions, ignore responsibilities, provide no feedback and allow authority to remain dormant. Laissez-faire is effective to use when employees are highly skilled, experienced as well as educated. Employees have pride in their work and they drive to do it successfully on their own, outside experts such as staff specialists or consultants are being used and employees are trustworthy as well as experienced (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asimwe & Zuena, 2023).

3. Methodology

The research is designed to employ a descriptive design, with both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Descriptive design concerns with describing situations as they are, and aimed at providing a description that is as factual and accurate as possible (Role, 2013).. The descriptive research design was used because it gives the information as it is without more alteration. The Quantitative approaches involved the collection of numerical data in order to explain phenomena of headmasters' leadership styles and secondary teachers' performance. Kerlinger (1986) was chosen to be used by the researcher for the relationship between the two variables, and it shows a systematic, controlled, empirical, and critical investigation of propositions about the presumed relationships between various phenomena.

3.1. Relationship between Headmasters' Leadership Style and Teachers' Performance

The relationship between headmasters' leadership styles and teachers' performance in Makindye division. The data analysis was done particularly using Pearson correlation analysis and multiple linear regressions. The study findings are summarized in table 1 and 2:

Table 1 Relationship between Headmasters' Leadership style and Teacher's Performance

		Headmasters' Leadership Style	Teachers' Performance
Headmaster's Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.352**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001
	N	87	87
Teacher's Performance	Pearson Correlation	-0.352**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	
	N	87	87

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The findings indicate that there is significant correlation (sig 0.000, $p = 0.05$) between the two variables, that is, headmaster's leadership style and teacher performance. It indicates that headmaster's leadership style and teacher performance have a low negative significant correlation coefficient of (-0.352).'' However, the findings indicated that there is a positive relationship between the headmasters' leadership style and the public secondary teacher's performance in Makindye division. That means the improvement to headmasters' leadership style tends to improve the teaching performance of teachers.

From the regression analysis the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.471$ which shows the 47.1% variation in teachers' performance is explained by changes in autocratic leadership style. This implies that any changes in autocratic leadership style would lead to 47.1% chance change in the teacher's performance. These results depict that autocratic leadership is significantly related with improved teachers. This supports that there is a positive association between leadership style and teachers' performance, Makindye secondary school in Uganda.

The results are supported by Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023)), explored that the democratic leadership style is the major style deployed by principals of Nigerian schools. The results were compared with the results of Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023)), who found that democratic style improves teachers' performance in secondary and primary schools. Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) it was found out that laissez-faire and democratic styles were frequently used by the head teachers. The study discovered that when heads engage in democratic style of leadership then teachers seem too satisfied with their specific jobs.

Table 2 Regression analysis of headmasters' leadership styles and teachers' performance in Makindye division

Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B		Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.990	0.259		11.562	0.000
	Democratic Leadership Style	0.213	0.060	0.355	3.585	0.001
	Autocratic Leadership Style	0.042	0.045	0.099	0.922	0.359
	Laissez-faire Leadership Style	-0.225	0.042	-0.509	-5.371	0.000

3.2. Democratic Leadership Style

Results in Table 2 based on regression Standardized Coefficients ($b = 0.355$, $p = 0.000$) indicate that when other factors in the model are held constant, the democratic leadership style significantly has a positive contribution of about 36% to the teachers' performance ($p < 0.05$). Democratic leadership style has a significant relationship with teachers' performance because it motivates the teachers as they share leadership with the headmaster through delegation of power, decision making, inspired by the headmaster in work and school team work.

The findings are in line with the study carried out by Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) indicated that majority of the respondents considered their headmasters in Nairobi public secondary schools to have democratic leadership behaviours. Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023)) describe the democratic headmasters as enthusiastic, conscientious, hardworking and well balanced in temperament, not aloof and very much in control albeit in a subtle manner. A study carried out Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023)) asserted the importance of airing complaints and grievances which can be a strategy of avoiding discipline problems among students. In the study some schools were found to have few discipline problems. This implies that there is a relationship between the style of leadership and teachers' performance not only that, but also students' discipline in schools. Most of the teachers' responses perceived their headmasters as democratic. The findings imply that most headmasters in Makindye division use democratic style.

Based on the results above, a democratic leadership encourages better teacher performance as compared to Autocratic leadership and Laissez-faire leadership. A leadership with no supervision negatively affects the teachers' performance. While the leadership with supervision affects the teachers' performance positively. Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) contended that this type of leadership is asserted to be the most punctual amongst other authority styles. The administrators examine with the subordinates before the issue general or expensive requests from subordinates don't hesitate to follow up on. The unrivalled permits the subordinates chance to utilize their drive and make commitments.

However, it was construed that fair participative sorts of administration is the best of all the authority styles as a result of the advantages that will be gotten from it by the workers in the midst of general results to the association all in all. That shows, even the secondary schools whose headmasters use democratic style make the teachers performance improve than those which use autocratic leadership style and laissez-faire leadership.

3.3. Autocratic Leadership Style

Results in Table 2 based on regression Standardized Coefficients ($b = 0.099$, $p = 0.359$) indicate that when other factors in the model are held constant, the autocratic leadership style does not significantly contribute to the teachers' performance ($p > 0.05$). Autocratic leadership style reveals that has no significant relationship with teachers' performance because P-value significant is greater than 0.05.

The findings also indicate that autocratic style of leadership is not highly favoured by majority of the headmasters as evidenced by the teachers and students' perceptions in Makindye division. The findings indicate that this style is not preferred by the majority as strict observance of rules, regulations and organizational policies overlooks the human factors. Extreme autocratic in some cases is considered a cause of indiscipline in some schools. Autocratic style of leadership suppresses freedom of discussion which can be a source of discontent thus leading discipline problems in school. Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) revealed that characteristics of closed climates can be likened to autocratic style of leadership, headmasters who have such characteristics tend to be impersonal while emphasizing on the need for hard work thus ignoring the grievances and complains of the followers. A study carried out by Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) to investigate the patterns of leadership responsible for different levels of performance by secondary schools in Uganda revealed that majority of the schools with ineffective performance used authoritarian patterns of leadership.

3.4. Laissez-faire Leadership Style

Results in Table 2 based on regression Standardized Coefficients ($b = -0.509$, $p = 0.000$) indicate that when other factors in the model are held constant, the Laissez-faire leadership style significantly has a negative contribution of about 51% to the teachers' performance ($p < 0.05$). Laissez-faire leadership shows to have an influence to teachers but can never affect their performance positively, even though is liked, it has a negative outcome.

The findings indicate that Laissez-Faire style Lunenburg and Ornestem Atasoy (2020); Sahim and Ozgenel (2020), (2021) Parveen, et al (2022) and Asiimwe and Zuena (2023) noted that, laissez-faire leader turns over almost all authority to group and does as little leading as possible. Given a situation in which the work to be done by each employee is clearly defined; such leaders maintain a hands-off policy. They make few attempts to increase productivity to their employees. This style is anti-thesis of the authoritarian style and is relationship oriented. Laissez-faire managers (heads) succumb to the sociological theory of management and McGregor's theory Y concept which argues that people are innately motivated, naturally like work and are interested in doing their work (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). The head who uses this style of management believes that there should be no rules and regulations since everybody has inborn senses of responsibility.

The manager who uses this style sets the people free so that the power Centre lacks the binding power. This style may lead to confusion anarchy or chaos. Perhaps this can be a mismanagement style and would hardly be conducive to provision of quality education. An institution whose head is a laissez faire leader is characterized by high degree of freedom of students and teachers. Cases of high indiscipline are very common and there is high level of don't care attitudes. Although communication is all channels, it's more so towards human relationships than relationships that facilitate a good learning environment, which enhances good performance (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023).

This means that laissez-fare style of leadership has some implications on the students' performance since it affects the school working environment. For example, in a school setting where the teachers have to set examinations, during a particular time, this might mean delay in evaluation and feedback since there are no sanctions to be followed for those who do not perform. On the other hand, the students might relax in different areas since they are free to do what they want. This might lead to lack of harmony in such a school set up (Ali, 2018; Halai, 2018; Demirauglu, 2018; Hague & Yamooah 2021; Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023). At times, the Laissez-faire leader is an abdicator who cares very little for achieving productivity goals or developing subordinates. The researcher says, at other times, Laissez faire style is appropriate and leads to high productivity. Such leadership situations include directing the work of highly skilled advertising copywriters, research scientists, or stock analysts. These individuals may neither require neither technical direction nor encouragement yet in the long run; even self-sufficient professionals require some feedback and recognition from their manager in order to sustain high performance Asiimwe & Zuena, 2023).

3.5. Testing the Hypothesis

The study hypothesized that; there is no significant relationship between headmasters' leadership style and teachers' performance in Makindye division secondary schools. Therefore, based on the findings the null hypothesis, was not supported it was rejected, after showing that there is a significant relationship between headmasters' leadership style and teachers' performance since the P-Value significance 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence the alternative which suggested that, "Headmaster leadership has a relationship with teacher performance was accepted.

4. Conclusion

The study concluded that the nature of the headmaster's leadership style is more of democratic and less autocratic style. This implied that the teachers are given freedom, sharing leadership, participating in decision making and having a team work. The study also concluded that, there is a moderate level of teachers' performance in Makindye division. This implied that, there is a moderate level of lesson preparations, assessing the students and moderate level of teachers' involvement in the co-curricular activities. Finally, the study concluded that; there is a strong positive relationship between the headmaster's leadership styles and the teachers' performance in Makindye division secondary schools.

The study recommends that, the headmasters should also practice laissez-faire leadership style since the headmasters did not practice it that is why the teacher's performance remained moderate. The study also recommends that the teachers should involve themselves in school co-curricular activities to motivate the students in studies and critical thinking. The study also recommends that the headmasters are to be given leadership training or induction through workshops, seminars so that they can know how to use different leadership styles in their schools for improving teaching/learning performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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